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Research Article

**PREFERENCE PROFILE OF HOMEOPATHY TO ALLOPATHY
IN POPULATION OF BAHAWALPUR**¹Dr. Shabana Bibi, ²Aqsa Rehman, ³Dr. Shehroz Ali Asghar¹Quaid e Azam Medical College Bahawalpur²Nishter Hospital Multan³BHU Dharor Muslim Muridke Sheikhupura**Abstract:**

Homeopathy is a system of complementary medicine in which ailments are treated by minute doses of natural substances that in larger amount would produce symptoms of ailments. Homeopathy is a therapeutic system that uses small doses of substances to stimulate auto-regulatory and self-healing process.

Objective: To find out the preference of population of Bahawalpur of Homeopathy to Allopathy.

Methodology: A sample of 100 patients was selected and sample was collected by Simple Random Sampling method. The duration of study was from March 2018 to April 2018. Subjects were the patients who came to homeopathic clinic for check-up and the method adopted was by pre-designed questionnaire. Data was analysed manually, frequency calculated and graphs were made. **Results:** A sample of 100 patients was taken. All of them responded to the questions. 85% used homeopathy and 15% allopathy. 44% used homeopathy because of its effectiveness, 22% preferred due to no side effects, 9% preferred due to its cheapness, 1% due to its better taste. 71% didn't use Homeopathy for the first time, 29% did use for the first time. 92% were cured from Homeopathy and 8% weren't cured. Entire family of 68% of patients sought homeopathic treatment. **Conclusion:** Patient beliefs and satisfaction are highly projecting people towards homeopathic treatment. Patients who are using homeopathic treatment in high percentage are with chronic diseases.

Key words: Homeopathy, allopathy.

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INTRODUCTION:

Homeopathy was introduced by a German doctor Samuel Hahnemann 200 years ago. It is based on law of similar described by him as "Let likes be cured by likes" and so named it homeopathy. His philosophy was minimal doses can relieve disease in those who have symptoms similar to those created by strong and potent doses of drugs. (2)

Herbal medicine has been in use since time in memorial and has remained a pillar content in health care system for the treatment of a range of diseases. Over the past decade, interest in drugs delivered from plants has greatly increased. It is estimated that 25% of all modern medicines are directly or indirectly delivered from plants. (3)

Approximately 80% of world's population relies on Herbal medicine to fulfil their daily health needs (Marshall, 1998). According to WHO, because of poverty and lack of access to modern medicine, about 65-85% of world's population which lives in developing countries depends on plants for primary health care (Akerle et al. 1993) and seemingly represent an important pillar of disease management. (3)

The world has very long, safe and continuous usage experience of many herbal drugs in the officially recognized alternative system of health, Ayurveda, Yoga, Sidhha, Homeopathy and Naturopathy. (4)

Effects of homeopathy were more than a placebo response. It has good rate of recovery, effective, considered cheap, less side effects, patient's satisfaction and length of consultation.(5)

So most people use this therapy and this is referred to as complementary and alternative medicine or traditional medicine.

WHO represents that traditional herbal preparation are popular in China which accounts for 30-50% of total medicine consumption. (6)

Furthermore, homeopathy is used for various viral illness, acute chronic conditions and many other skin ailments, cancer treatment, disease caused by Trypanosomacruzi, diabetes, menstrual irregularities and other conditions like upper and lower respiratory tract allergies and ear complaints. Thus it's considered Pseudoscience. (8)

Moreover, in synthetic drug usage, public seems to be fed up due to only symptomatic relief, completion of Rx, increase rate of side effects and high cost

whereas in homeopathy, there is ease in administration of dose, high acceptability, best effectiveness and no side effects. (9)

Literature Review:

Homeopathy is a therapeutic system that uses small doses of substances to stimulate auto-regulatory and self-healing process that has been for 200 years based on three principles similarity, minimum doses and symptomatic totality. WHO defines CAM as the general continuation of types of health care that are not part of tradition of a country and that are not integrated into the dominant health care system.(1)

In a study conducted in Brazil and prevalence of the use of homeopathy by the population of Monte Carlos, Minas Gerais, Brazil, the main health problems found in this group; hypertension (9.4%), allergy (5.4%) and bronchitis (5.4%) followed by depression, sinusitis and hypercholesterolemia. The main reason to seeking was conventional treatment did not have any side effects cost is reasonable and 73% satisfied. (1)

Another research conducted in Kenya "Factors associated with the use of Herbal medicine among patients in herbal clinics in Gucha district, Kenya shows that majority of respondents (58.3%) had completed secondary school while (34.7%) had only primary education with regards to their occupation (34.7%) were farmer and (38.3%) retail traders. (3)

In the study conducted in Malaysia "The use of complementary and alternative medicine among patients with chronic disease at out-patient clinics that a large number of patients were married (85%) had children (90.7%). The other type of CAM used by the patients were herbal drugs (24.9%), Yoga (2.8%), traditional Chinese medicine (3.4%), tai chi (2.5%), prayer healing (18.7%), qigong (1.56%), and meditation (0.93%) etc.

17.6% had family history, patients having adult children that are using their source by income that influenced parents to start CAM. The patients with chronic diseases (63.9%) are using CAM. (6)

In a study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan "Concept of homeopathy among general population in Karachi, Pakistan" shows that female were in slight majority (53.5%) than males (46.5%). Among them 70% were married with Muslim predominance. More than half of total respondents were either housewives or were related to teaching profession with a highest number in age group between 31-45 years. Monthly income

of patients was between RS.5000-15000 out of 135 patients who had homeopathic treatment in past, half of them had homeopathic treatment on advice by others and (24.4%) had it as it is preferred in family. A majority of participants (41.5%) preferred homeopathy for chronic diseases followed by 24.4% for GIT, Liver, UIT; while 13.3% preferred homeopathy for acute illness.(8)

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

The design of study was Descriptive study. The study setting selected was Homeopathic clinic at one unit chowk, Bahawalpur. The duration of study was from March 2018 to April 2018. Subjects were the patients who came to homeopathic clinic for check-up and the method adopted was by pre-designed questionnaire. A sample of 100 patients was selected and sample was collected by Simple Random Sampling method.

As of 2018, medical students of Quaid-e-Azam Medical collage spent two months in the study of preference profile of homeopathic medicine. At the end of one month period, students filled a pre-designed questionnaire of 23 questions to assess the level of preference of homeopathy compared to allopathy. Data of questionnaire was collected by simple random sampling (100 questionnaire) after taking consent. Patients of both gender who were willing to give data were included in study and those unwilling were excluded. Researcher translated and then retranslated the form and added answers for convenience of subjects. Data was analysed manually, frequency calculated and graphs were made.

RESULTS:

The research was about determining the factors associated with the preference of homeopathic treatment to allopathic treatment.

A sample of 100 patients was taken. All of them responded to the questions. Out of these, 28% were females and 72% were males. 74% belonged to middle class having income more than RS.10000,

11% having less than RS.5000 and 15% having RS.5000-10,000 . 12% were illiterate, 35% had primary school education, 12% matriculates and 41% graduates

85% used homeopathy and 15% allopathy. 44% used homeopathy because of its effectiveness, 22% preferred due to no side effects, 9% preferred due to its cheapness, 1% due to its better taste . 71% didn't use Homeopathy for the first time, 29% did use for the first time.

92% were cured from Homeopathy and 8% weren't cured. Entire family of 68% of patients sought homeopathic treatment. The family of remaining 32% didn't seek homeopathic treatment. 61% patients didn't use homeopathy and allopathy simultaneously and 39% patients did use homeopathy and allopathy simultaneously. 57% of patients had emergency in their family, 43% had no emergency in their family.

63% were vaccinated and 37% were not . Among them, 9% were using allopathic vaccine, 9% homeopathic. According to this research, majority of patients didn't see any set-back of using homeopathic treatment, 12% suffered. Because of more effectiveness and satisfaction, 89% recommended homeopathy to others, 11% didn't.

Regarding occupation, 49% had government jobs, 21% farmers, 20% house-wives and 10% students. 74% didn't know about composition of homeopathic drugs 26% had knowledge. The main reason of using homeopathic treatment was the easy accessibility; 60% for homeopathy, 26% for allopathy, 14% for both.

55% of the patients first came by homeopathic treatment by seeking advice from someone, 16% by seeing someone getting better by this treatment. Among Homeopathic users, 86% never suffered from this treatment and 14% suffered. Among Allopathic users, 51% never suffered due to its usage and 49% suffered. 92% of the patients were cured due to homeopathic treatment and 8% didn't.

DISCUSSION:

The objective of our research was to determine the preference profile of homeopathic to allopathic treatment. A sample of 100 patients was collected from Saeed Homeo-clinic, Satellite town, Bahawalpur. In this sample, age range was 6-60 years.

In this research, the number of males was greater than that of females. But in a similar study conducted in Karachi, female users were dominant (1); and in a study conducted in Kenya, males were dominant. (3)

According to this research, 88% didn't face any setback of homeopathic treatment and a similar research conducted in Brazil showed that majority of patients didn't face any setbacks. (1)

In this research, majority of patients were graduates and according to another researched carried out in Kenya, majority had completed their secondary school education. (3)

Research showed that majority had government jobs and a study conducted in Kenya showed majority of patients was retail traders. (3) Majority had income above RS. 10,000 and study conducted in Karachi showed that monthly income of majority of patients was in between RS. 5000- 15,000. (8) 55% of patients used homeopathy when someone advised them and according to study conducted in Karachi, majority used on the advice of others. (3) By this research, majority were using homeopathic treatment because their family was taking same treatment and according to a study conducted in Malaysia, majority was having positive family history. (6)

The main cause of using alternative medication than allopathy is its high cost, lack of effectiveness, more side effects, lack of proper income and accessibility.

CONCLUSION:

Patients who are using homeopathic treatment in high percentage are with chronic diseases. Variables such as age groups, education level, household income, large family, employment status of patient are significantly associated with homeopathic use. Patient beliefs and satisfaction are highly projecting people towards homeopathic treatment. The lack of effectiveness and drastic side effects of allopathy are causing patients to seek alternative ways of treatment.

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